

LINGUISTIC DESCRIPTION OF WORD FORMATION IN PARTICULAR OF WORD DERIVATION

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ANNOTATION

In the work, specific views on the explanation of the theoretical foundations of the relation of language and speech phenomena to the derivation are presented. In the same way that the units that appear as linguistic units, but have communicative-significant properties other than nominative-denotative properties, are recorded as predicative units, specific opinions are expressed about their propositional structure.

KEY WORDS: lexical unit, word formation methods, affixation, composition, grammaticalization, lexemalization, operator, operand, derivative, derivation, derivatology, abbreviation, root word.

A word with its lexical feature, lexical possibility, referring or pointing property, its possibilities in language and speech, its functional value in the text, discursive power, nominative, predicative, communicative, cognitive, pragmatic and a number of other similar aspects is a research based on a purely linguistic approach in linguistics. is a worthy object. In the process of studying and teaching word formation, many people hesitated for a long time whether it is a separate field of linguistics or one of the issues related to morphology. Therefore, in existing textbooks and other linguistic resources, cases where word formation is studied within morphology [1. -B. 25-78.] and in contrast to this, we can witness that the issue of word formation is covered in a separate chapter[11]. In the following years, word formation is given in a separate section in textbooks, manuals and other books.

At least two constituent components are involved in the creation of a current (synchronized) word, at least one of which is capable of expressing an independent meaning, i.e. an object, sign, action, etc. It is also mentioned in this and other sources that it is called a singular formation (formative word). It is important to note that the independent meaningful part that participates in the creation of the construction is considered to be the constituent base (the base of the construction), and it can be observed that such a base is one in a simple construction and more than one in a compound word (workman: ish -

constructional base, -chi - constructional affix, worker - construction ; coal: the building base - stone and coal, coal - construction) [11, -B.168].

U.Tursunov, A.Mukhtorov, Sh.Rakhmatullaev's textbook "Current Uzbek Literary Language" contains detailed information about word formation, according to which the vocabulary of the language is enriched by newly created words, the meaning of a word changes, and it is used in a different way. creating a new word - this shows that word formation is related to lexicology, [7] it is argued.

This opinion presented above is significant because it has a different aspect than the opinions mentioned in Sh.Shoabdurahmanov's textbook. Because the process of word creation is not just a process or event related to the external, that is, formal change of the unit being created, it is noted that one of the most important aspects is the change in meaning.

In addition, U.Tursunov, A.Mukhtorov, Sh.Rakhmatullaev's textbook "Current Uzbek Literary Language" shows how grammar controls the process of word formation, determines which word group new words belong to, the relationship between word formation and form formation within each group, word formation and it is specially noted that the use of the same or similar affixes in form formation shows that the word formation section is directly related to morphology, and other ways of word formation show that it is related to phonetics and syntax [7].

So, it begins to appear that it is impossible to fully understand the essence of the matter with the approach that the process of word formation implies the formation of an independent word. We have our own reasons for expressing this opinion. Because any changes related to the formation of words cause the need to consider not only morphological, but also lexical, semantic, semiotic and syntactic changes.

In the description of word formation, the issues of single and multiple meaning of word-forming affixes also require a specific approach to a certain extent. In this case, although they are the same in form, the issue of creating words with one or more meanings in content is also a separate research aspect.

From the above-mentioned monographs, textbooks, dissertations and other literature, it can be concluded that the issue of artificial words has always been the center of attention of linguists in linguistics. The scientific-theoretical achievements that arose as a result of such interests served for the dynamics of the development of science both in its time and in subsequent periods.

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